

Major Tourist Attraction in Parbhani District - A Geographical Analysis (MS)

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Abstract:

In this paper studied of Major Tourism in Parbhani District. The natural and cultural resources, God temples, Man made tourist stations, waterfalls, temples, historical Places, Natural wild-life, hill ranges and amenable climate are very important resources of tourist attraction in this district. The various facilities available to the domestic and foreign tourists in Parbhani district, these include natural resources, transportation, infrastructure, hospitality resources and major tourist attractions. For the research work Parbhani District is selected. This district has at Parbhani its Beed district at West, Jalna and Buldhana District at North, Hingoli and Nanded district East, Latur district south. The object of study region is, to highlight the attractive tourist destinations and religious places, Natural, Historical and Cultural Place etc. This study based on primary and secondary data. Tourist attractions in the district as is, natural beauty, southern Palam Gangakhed and Sonpeth tahsils of Balaghat range and Northan tahsils as a Selu and Jintur Ajantha-verul range of Sayhyadri mountain, temples, mini garden, tracking, rock climbing, wild life, festival's fairs, Dams etc. places. To the stay of tourist which requires natural sources, infrastructural and transportation facilities, accommodation, food, recreation, sightseeing, shopping and variety of facilities and services for use and enjoyments. The source of tourism depends on all these facilities available in this study region.

Keywords: Tourism, Transportation, Cultural, Parbhani District, Recourses

Introduction:

The study region consists of multiple layers of solidified fluid basalt and is more than 2,000 meters thick and formed between 60 to 68 million years ago during the Cretaceous period, No systematic geological mapping of the district has yet been taken up by the geological survey of India, Information available is only through the reports submitted by the officers of the geological survey of India in connection with their visits for studying groundwater position of certain areas engineering geological aspects of some dam-sites lieutenant - colonel Sykes (1839) in this contribution to the geology of western area makes brief mention of the general geology of Parbhani district. The entire district is occupied by basaltic lava-flows erupted in the Cretaceous-Eocene age which are popularly as known as Deccan traps. Intrusive basic dykes, basalt lava, flows belonging to Deccan trap volcanic episode, associated with intertrapean beds, red bole beds, porous ash and cretaceous matter etc. Basaltic rock is found in some part of the Parbhani districts for want of geological mapping in the area flow pattern and fabric of basaltic exposed in the district are not known. Parbhani district covers 6511 square kilometers area. Physiography is one of the dominant parameter of physical environment. The relief of the district has an immense variety not to be witnessed to the some extent in many other districts of the state. The Jintur range is the more prominent portion in the heights of the district. It is a remnant plateau with a general trend from west north-west to south south-east and forms a part of the Ajanta ranges emanating from the Sahyadri. The

crest line consists of flat tops at an average elevation of 533.75 m. above sea level but here and there rounded peaks record heights up to 549 meters and 579.70 m. above sea level.

The scarp-lands lying to the north of the Purna area are counterparts of the Jintur hills, but they are more continuous and have an undulating plateau extension towards the north. Both the Jintur hills and these northern counterparts have several gaps or pass which allow communications and favor the growth of Gap towns. The district as a whole belongs to the Godavari peninsular drainage, but the area of the district mainly belongs to two river systems, one in the north and north-east the Penganga, and the other the Marathwada Purna and other immediate tributaries of the Godavari flowing in this district. In this paper studied of Major Tourism in Parbhani District. The natural and cultural resources, God temples, Man made tourist stations, waterfalls, temples, historical Places, Natural wild-life, hill ranges and amenable climate are very important resources of tourist attraction in this district. The various facilities available to the domestic and foreign tourists in Parbhani district, these include natural resources, transportation, infrastructure, hospitality resources and major tourist attractions. For the research work Parbhani District is selected.

Objective of the Study:

The present research Paper has been undertaken to make on in-depth study of major tourism place in Parbhani district. The main objectives of the study were as follows-

1. To study the profile of Parbhani district.

2. To highlight places in study area.
3. To review the progress of tourism in Parbhani district.

Study Area:

Parbhani district is selected for present study. The choice of topic under investigation is influenced by many considerations. Firstly Parbhani district comprising the nine tahsil of Maharashtra state has a significant location on south-east of Maharashtra plateau. Nine tahsil are considered for the study region in Parbhani district is covered by rough topography and the remaining part have flat surface. Balaghat range is southern part in Gangakhed and

Palam tahsil. Purna and Godavari rivers basin are useful for agricultural activities and Ajanta range in northern part in Jintur tahsil. All these consideration motivated the author turn his attention this region and its agricultural geography. Parbhani district located between 18°45' north to 20°01' North latitudes and 76°13' east to 77°29' East longitude (Map No.1). The area of study region is 6511 km², which is 2.11 percent of the whole area of the state. The population in the study region is 1836086 population in (2012 census) which is 1.63 percent of total population in Maharashtra.

Map No 1. Location and Boundaries of Parbhani District

Hypothesis:

Tourism can generate employment opportunities especially in the overall of the Parbhani district.

Data Base and Methodology:

The Primary data was collected from two visits the various tourist centers taken photographs and sample tourists. Secondary data was collected from reference books review, magazines, research report, internet, thesis etc. Tourist Attractions in the District some important tourist centers in the Parbhani. The present research paper work author has been used the following method to calculate different aspects.

Explanation:

A. Nature and Cultural Place

1. **Yeldari Dam:** Jintur Tahsil Yeldari Dam is located at a distance of about 15 km. at a distance of about 55 km. from Parbhani. The dam was built between 1958 and 1968, It has a hydroelectric power station consisting of three units of 7.5MV capacity each for 22.5 MW total capacity. Water from the dam is used for irrigation as well as for producing electricity operated by Government pondered Power Company. The area is a perfect spot for picnic, with scenic surrounding, unexploited Ajantha verul east-west Sahyadri hilly terrains, Dam

is renovated and developed as a reservoir and also tourist attraction spot in Parbhani district.

2. Masuli Dam: Gangakhed tahsil Masuli Dam is very beautiful view point. There is a calava on this Dam and it's on mauli river, this is look like a fish there fore called Masuli Dam. Dam is 15 to 20 km from Gangakhed, we can go from two side at this view point. One from Akoli and another way from Isad we can go from Khoklewadi as well . Turist are private vehicle bike or four -wheeler and it is about 5.20 km. away from the Gangakhed railway station. This is very beautiful place. We can see their peacocks, heron, Fish. It's nice place for one day trip. It's only in rainy season.

3. Karpara Dam : Karpara dam is an earth fill dam on Karpara river near Jintur tahsil. The height of the dam above lowest foundation is 54.7 ft. while the length is 1,046 m. The volume content is 344 km³ and gross storage capacity is 27,320.00 km³ and also tourist attraction spot in Parbhani district.

4. Indrayani Hill: Indrayani Hill is great places to go near Parbhani city. This is the femus of indrayani male of balaghat mount ion range. This hill station was a natural beautiful place in the Parbhani tahsil and it is dome size sheep of mount ion. The surrounding the agricultural field and water conservation projects as a pani adwa pani jirava projects. Many local tourists are visited on this natural tourist place.

5. Nemgiri Hill: Nemgiri is located Jintur tahsil it is nearby Jintur city from northern direction from 2 km. This is natural tourism place. Nemgiri is named Neminatha is for Nemi while giri means mountain. However, there is some historical knowledge available about the caves. Many tourists are visited come from Aurangabad, Jalna, Parbhani and Nanded district. This is actually two hills on Nemgiri hill station.

6. Jambhul Bet: The Jamghul Island is a scenic place situated in the middle of Godvari river basin and has water on all sides. This is only one island in Marathwada , Truly the alchemy of nature is heavy. To reach Jambhul Island, you have to go by boat. It is a scenic place Palum tahsil in Parbhani district. There is an inexhaustible rush of tourists from all over the state to experience the wonderful creations of nature on this island and Vehicles available from Palam. This island has an ancient temple of Maruti right in the center surrounded by purple trees and flocks of peacocks and other birds. The trees on the island have not been planted by anyone before but they have come naturally through the spread of seeds by animals and birds. This island is also important in terms of biodiversity.

7. Charthana: The Charthana tourist place is a Village in nearby Jintur Taluka in Parbhani District of Maharashtra. It belongs to Marathwada region. It is located 55 km towards North from District head

quarters Parbhani and 18 km from Jintur. The Charthana tourist place is a natural Visitation and animals, birds are available on the observation of natural beauty.

B. Historical Place and Religious Places:

1. Pardeshwar Temple: The Pardeshwar Temple as a Mercury Shivlinga in Parbhani city. This temple is built of marble by Sri Swami Sachchidandji Saraswati. The huge temple is dedicated to Lord Shiva with Eighty foot of height. The uniqueness of the temple is that main shrine Shivlinga is made of two fifty kg of Para mines Mercury and one of the largest Shivlinga of India. This Shivlinga made of Para is called as Tejoling and has equal religious importance of Twelve Jyotirlinga in the India.

2. Hazrat Turabul Haq Dargah Parbhani: The Hazrat Turabul Haq Dargah is best known for its annual fair which has history of 108 years. The thousands of followers of all religions and faiths gather between two February to fifteen February every each year. In Parbhani this dargah is the symbol of unity between all religions. People from across the state visits the dargah. Because of huge popularity of dargah in Maharashtra state, it is often called as "Ajmer Sharif of Maharashtra". Thousands of diseased persons visit this dargah in the hope of healthy life.

3. Shri Saibaba Temple: The Sai Baba was born in Pathri tahsil city in Parbhani District. In 1970s, a field research established that Shri Saibaba Temple, Sri Sai Smarak Samiti was then formed in Pathri. A committee purchased land for temple on site of Sai Baba's house and construction of the temple was started in 1994. In 1999 the temple was inaugurated to the public

4. Mudgaleshwar Temple: The one of the religious place to visit in Parbhani district is the famous temple of lord Mudgaleshwar this is one of the historical temple in the Parbhani. This temple is situated on the bank of the Godavari River. Peoples make a holy bath in the Godavari River. Every Mahashivratri lots of devotees come there for Mudgaleshwar Darshan. The make a spiritual atmosphere in and around of the surrounding.

5. Shri Narsimha Mandir: The Pokharni is situated about 18 km. from Parbhani. The Narasimhadeva temple draws throngs of pilgrims from Andhra Pradesh and other surrounding states, which can travel easily by car or rail to this holy site. While the temple compound is quite large, the gabhara is very small a three foot by four foot room. The entrance is equally small, and devotees must squat to see the Lord through a three foot high entrance. His darshan here at Pokharni is also somewhat difficult.

6. Neminath Digambar Jain Mandir: Shri Neminath Digambar Jain Temple Nawagaad is famous for the ancient and artistic architecture of Lord Neminath. Earlier it was situated in the village

of Ukhalad, which is about two km from the banks of Purna River. The inner part of the temple is covered with a mirror and it is very beautiful

7. Shri Digambar Jain Atishaya Kshetra Nemgiri: There are two hills named Nemgiri & Chandragiri are famous in the world for their ancient artistic and miraculous Jain Cave Temples & Chaityalayas. In ancient times this area was famous as Jainpur, this was developed in the time of Emperor; today two temples out of them only are present. The surrounding the agricultural field and water conservation projects as a pani adwa pani jirava projects. Many local tourists are visited on this natural tourist place.

Conclusion:

Parbhani district many Natural and cultural, Historical, Religious tourist Places are available of the tourism Occupation. To the stay of tourist for several days, which requires natural re-sources, infrastructural and transportation facilities, accommodation, sightseeing, shopping and variety of facilities and services for use and enjoyments? The success of tourism depends on all these facilities. District wise various tourist attractions in the district consisting of temples, festivals, fairs, art and dams, caves, creeks, lakes, hill-stations etc. Week-long dream journey of Deccan odyssey and royal facilities provided to tourist. Eco tourism is environmentally responsible tourism, which must incorporate the Nature based and ecologically, socially, culturally and economically sustainable. The various promotional activities were conducted to encourage ecotourism. The lastly about overall explained tourist attractions and the tourism activity generates employment opportunities in various part of study area in Parbhani District.

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